

THE STRUCTURE OF MOLECULAR COMPOUNDS. PART I. THE MAGNETIC
SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF THE MOLECULAR COMPOUNDS OF
SYMMETRICAL TRINITROBENZENE WITH
HYDROCARBONS AND PHENOLS

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Magnetic susceptibilities of the molecular compounds of *sym*-trinitrobenzene with hydrocarbons and phenols have been measured and the results discussed in relation to the structure of the molecular compounds.

The structure of molecular compounds formed by the union of two different substances has been the subject of much speculation. Lowry (*Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 218) suggested that molecular compounds were obtained by the intermolecular co-ordination. Bennet and Wills (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 256) supporting the above view, pointed out that the deeper colour of the molecular compounds and the simple stoichiometric ratios in which the components were present were further evidence for the chemical linkage. The electronic formulation of these molecular compounds was based on the suggestion that the nitro group with structure (I) is capable of acquiring structure (II) under certain conditions of activation

The nitrogen of the nitro group in the activated state can thus accept a pair of electrons from amino group of amines and the compound is represented as

In case of molecular compounds of trinitrobenzene with hydrocarbons, one of the double bonds of hydrocarbons acts in the polarised form as

and donates a pair of electrons for the co-ordinate linkage. These views got further support from dipole moment and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Polarisation P_{AB} of molecular compounds is greater than the sum of polarisation P_A and P_B , which can only be accounted for by electronic changes (Weiss, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 64).

Bhatnagar and co-workers (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1934, 9, 131) have measured the magnetic susceptibilities of a few picrates. They attribute the differences (varying from 7.7×10^{-6} to 14.4×10^{-6}) between χ_{MAB} and the sum of χ_M and χ_{Mf} to constitutive correction constant for co-ordinate linkage.

Recently, however, much evidence has been adduced against the formation of these compounds through a semipolar bond. Absorption spectra of molecular compounds of *m*-dinitrobenzene and picric acid with a number of hydrocarbons (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1576) indicated that they were merely superimposition of curves of two components and neither the position of maxima nor $\log K$ indicated anything more than a small interaction. X-ray studies of *p*-iodoaniline-trinitrobenzene compound (Powell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 153) showed that intermolecular distances were greater than 3.5 Å which excludes the possibility of any chemical bonds between molecules. Briegleb and co-workers (*Z. Physik*, 1932, 19, 255 ; 1934, 26, 63) after extensive investigations on the heats of interaction, dissociation, and combination concluded that the forces involved in molecular compound formation were those of interaction between a strongly polar group of one component and induced dipole in the other. The electrostatic forces thus involved are intermediate between Van der Waal's forces of attraction and true co-valencies.

In view of these later developments, a detailed magnetic study of molecular compounds therefore seemed desirable. The authors have determined χ_M of compounds of trinitrobenzene with hydrocarbons and phenols with a view to discussing their structures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The molecular compounds of *sym*-trinitrobenzene were obtained by mixing the alcoholic solutions of the components in molecular proportions and boiling the mixture for a requisite time. The product was crystallised 3 or 4 times. Great care was taken to avoid any decomposition during crystallisation.

The susceptibilities were measured by the modified form of Guoy's balance (*cf.* Nevgi, *Current Sci.*, 1935, 4, 403). Conductivity water with $\chi_M = -72.10^{-6}$ was taken as the reference substance and the method was standardised by making determinations on compounds of known susceptibilities. The results of χ_M of known compounds with % error are reported in Table I, χ_M of molecular compounds and components in Table II, and comparison between χ_M of compound and sum of χ_M of the components in Table III.

TABLE I

Substance.	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$		
	(Mean of three obs.)	Reported'	Deviation
KCl	0.514	0.514	0.0%
<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene	0.350	0.352	0.6
Naphthalene	0.719	0.717	0.3
Camphoric anhydride	0.624	0.622	0.3
Ethyl alcohol	0.743	0.744	0.1

TABLE II

R = Trinitrobenzene

No.	Substance	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$		
		per gram. Mean of three readings	per g. mol. experi- mental	per g. mol. reported
1.	R-Naphthalene	0.4781	163.03	..
2.	R-Methylnaphthalene	0.48317	171.52	..
3.	R-Nitronaphthalene	0.4333	167.2	..
4.	R-Bromonaphthalene	0.4491	188.66	..
5.	R-Phenanthrene	0.4916	192.21	..
6.	R-Anthracene	0.47729	186.62	..
7.	R-Flourene	0.4522	171.38	..
8.	R-Benzidine	0.4765	189.17	..
9.	R- α -Naphthol	0.4566	163.0	..
10.	R- β -Naphthol	0.46212	164.97	..
11.	R-Salol	0.4572	195.22	..
12.	R-Anthranilic acid	0.4107	143.64	..
13.	α -Naphthalene	0.719	92.03	91.77
14.	β -Methylnaphthalene	0.7231	102.66	..
15.	α -Nitronaphthalene	0.6683	97.97	97.67
16.	β -Bromonaphthalene	0.596	123.37	123.78
17.	Phenanthrene	0.719	127.98	127.8
18.	Anthracene	0.724	128.87	129.22
19.	Flourene	0.688	111.02	110.39
20.	Benzidine	0.626	115.18	..
21.	α -Naphthol	0.6708	96.595	96.91
22.	β -Naphthol	0.6722	96.79	96.91
23.	Salol	0.5777	123.62	..
24.	Anthranilic acid	0.5484	75.15	..
25.	Trinitrobenzene	0.350	74.55	74.97

TABLE III

Comparison between χ_M of molecular compound and sum of χ_M of components

No.	Compounds.	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$ (obs.)	Sum of χ_M of components.	Diff. between obs. and additive values.
1.	R-Naphthalene	163.03	166.58	— 3.55
2.	R-Methylnaphthalene	171.52	177.21	— 5.69
3.	R-Nitronaphthalene	167.2	172.52	— 5.32
4.	R-Bromonaphthalene	188.66	197.922	— 9.262
5.	R-Phenanthrene	192.21	202.52	—10.32
6.	R-Anthracene	186.62	203.42	—16.8
7.	R-Flourene	171.38	185.57	—14.19
8.	R-Benzidine	189.17	189.73	— 0.56
9.	R- α -Naphthol	163.0	171.145	— 8.14
10.	R- β -Naphthol	164.976	171.37	— 6.4
11.	R-Salol	195.22	198.17	— 2.95
12.	R-Anthranilic acid	143.64	149.70	— 6.06

DISCUSSION

It is clear from the values shown in Table III that these molecular compounds are less diamagnetic than the sum of the molecular diamagnetism of their components. These results are contrary to the observations of Bhatnagar, Verma and Kapur (*loc. cit.*), who showed that the molecular compounds are in general more diamagnetic than the sum of χ_M of their components. It is further evident from a close perusal of the differences tabulated in the last column of Table III that these differences increase in the order :

anthracene>flourene>phenanthrene>naphthalene>benzidine. As shown by Briegleb this is also the order of their increasing anisotropic polarisabilities.

If the molecular compound formation were due to any definite chemical interaction or the establishment of a co-ordinate linkage between the components, the difference should have been nearly the same in every case.

According to Briegleb (*loc. cit.*) the components in molecular compounds are held by forces akin to Van der Waal's type arising from the electrostatic interaction of the permanent dipole of one component and the induced dipole of the other. If this were the case, only small differences between the experimental and additive χ_M values of the molecular compounds could be expected. It would, however, be seen that in the case of many compounds (Table III) the differences are quite large. It appears therefore that forces altogether different from those postulated by the previous workers are responsible for the formation of molecular complexes. It is probable that the various resonance forms of the components play an important part in the formation of the molecular complexes. If we take into account the relative contributions of the different forms of the components, the increase or decrease in the χ_M of the complexes from the sum of the χ_M of their components can be satisfactorily explained.

sym-Trinitrobenzene can exist in the following forms

Calculations for the theoretical diamagnetism by Gray and Cruickshank's methods (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 1491) for the form I are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

No. of atoms.	Charge on each.	Diamagnetism of each			Total diamagnetism.	Bond depression.	Resultant molecular diamagnetism.
3C	-0.04	C ⁻	0.04 × 14.69	= 0.587	} = 10.149	30.447	
		C ⁰	0.96 × 9.96	= 9.562			
3H	0.04	H ⁺	0.04 × 0	= 0	} = 2.278	6.834	
		H ⁰	0.96 × 2.372	= 2.278			
3N	1.28	N ⁺	0.28 × 4.12	= 1.1536	} = 5.4088	16.227	3C=C = 28.50
		N ⁺	0.72 × 5.91	= 4.2552			
3O	-0.34	O ⁻	0.34 × 9.40	= 3.1960	} = 7.875	23.625	3C-C = 5.94
		O ⁻	0.34 × 9.40	= 3.1960			
3C	0.06	C ⁰	0.66 × 7.09	= 4.6794	} = 9.7608	29.283	3N-C = 5.34
		C ⁺	0.06 × 6.64	= 0.3984			
3O	-1.0	O ⁰	0.94 × 9.96	= 9.3624	} = 9.40	28.200	3N→O = 1.56
		<i>Vide table</i>					
					134.616	-84.63	49.986

The calculations for the other forms are done in the same way and the values are shown below the formulae. The mean of the above calculated values is -75.22 which agrees with the experimental value of -74.8 (*vide* Table II). The above resonance structures therefore contribute equally to the equilibrium state of trinitrobenzene. The molecular diamagnetism of the polarised form (structure II) is greater than those of the other forms. Under proper conditions of activation which are provided by the presence of the second anisotropic and polarisable component, there is juxtaposition in the relative contributions of the above structures.

We take naphthalene as the second component for the sake of discussion. It has been shown by Gray and Cruickshank (*loc. cit.*) from calculations similar to those given above that the experimental diamagnetism of naphthalene (91.77×10^{-6}) corresponds to the structure in which one of the two rings is in internal ionic form and the other in the double bonded (Kekule's) form. In naphthalene there is resonance between the diamagnetically equal structures I(a) and I(b).

Each ring exists for half the time in the internal ionic form and for the other half in the double bonded form, *i.e.* in each ring resonance between internal ionic and double bonded structure occurs. Theoretical diamagnetism for naphthalene with both rings in the double bonded form comes out to be 57.716.

The molecular compound formation between T.N.B. and naphthalene is probably due to the greater resonance contribution of the polarised form of T.N.B. *i.e.* structure II than the other structures (I or III) and a complementary effect on naphthalene due to the electrostatic induction by virtue of which the internal ionic character of naphthalene molecule is depressed. The increased resonance energy under the above energy conditions gives stability to the molecular combination of trinitrobenzene and naphthalene. The fact that the trinitrobenzene-naphthalene compound is less diamagnetic than the sum of χ_M of its components is explained by the fact that the decrease in diamagnetism brought about by the depression of the internal ionic character of naphthalene is more than the increase due to the polarised form of T.N.B. The presence of substituent groups in naphthalene would affect the polarisability of the naphthalene nucleus, and therefore the magnitude of the depression of the internal ionic character of naphthalene would be affected by the nature of the substituent group or groups present. The observed varying differences from additivity are therefore not unexpected.

The molecular compound formation between trinitrobenzene and anthracene can be similarly interpreted. The accepted structure for anthracene is

The following are the possible interionic resonance structures for anthracene, based on the internal ionic character of the double bonded form in aromatic nuclei. Theoretical diamagnetism for these structures is calculated in the same way as given above.

I
101.71

II
112.62

III
119.26

IV
143.949

Theoretical diamagnetism for the structure with all the rings in Kekule's double bonded form comes out to be 76.42. The experimental value of diamagnetism of anthracene (128.87) however, shows that contribution of the internal ionic forms to the equilibrium state of anthracene is considerable.

The big difference of 16.8 units (*vide* Table III) between the experimental and the additive sum of χ_w for anthracene-trinitrobenzene compound is as explained in the case of naphthalene due to the greater internal ionic character and anisotropic polarisability of anthracene molecule.

In the formation of the molecular compounds the decrease effected in the internal ionic character of the aromatic hydrocarbons would be proportional to their anisotropic polarisabilities, because the polarisability and anisotropy will depend on the induced effect of the polarised nitro group. The fact that the differences from additivity in case of these molecular compounds increase in the increasing order of the anisotropic polarisability of the aromatic hydrocarbons lends support to the views discussed above about the structure and mechanism for the molecular compound formation. The structure of other molecular compounds can be similarly interpreted.